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The Influence of Children's and Adolescent Literature in Indonesia in the Formation of Character: A Hermeneutic Study

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Abstract

Children's and adolescent literature are two genres in literature that are different in terms of their goals, themes and writing. Children's and youth literature in Indonesia has become an interesting subject in literary studies. So, the aim of this research is to determine the influence of children's and youth literary works in forming character. This research uses a qualitative descriptive research design. Then the researcher carried out an analysis of fables in children's literature and novels in youth literature. The results of the research show that children's literature and youth literature have an influence on character formation. Literary works have many uses and benefits for life. Apart from that, literary works are useful because they can be a recreational means for readers and viewers, and the process of enjoying them will bring calm and maturity to the soul through studying the contents of literary works. In this way, the moral messages, attitudes, behavior and personality depicted in literary works will give rise to a full soul in them, which will ultimately lead the learner to change the character values of children and adolescents.

Keyword: Literature; Child; Teenager; Character; Hermeneutic

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INTRODUCTION

Research Problem

Children's and youth literature in Indonesia has become an interesting subject in literary studies, especially in the context of trends, emerging issues, and their influence in shaping the nature of the younger generation. In the midst of changing times and technological developments, literature has played an important role in shaping the thoughts, values and attitudes of children and adolescents.

However, the problem that arises is the extent to which children's and youth literature in Indonesia is able to face the challenges of the times, deal with emerging issues and provide a positive influence in forming the character of the younger generation. Thus, this research will focus on the analysis of children's and youth literature, highlighting the issues that arise, and identifying their influence in shaping the character of children and youth in Indonesia.

Importance of Research for Field

In the field context, this research has important relevance. The influence of Indonesian children's and youth literature in character formation is important because they help in developing children's personal values, increasing literacy culture, and increasing awareness of the importance of the Indonesian language. As an effort to build character and develop children's personalities, literary reading materials have an important role. In the context of social media use, the language used can influence teenagers. Using good and correct language on social media can help increase awareness of the importance of the Indonesian language and help in developing a literacy culture. So overall, this research strengthens understanding of the importance of children's and youth literature in shaping the character of Indonesia's young generation.

Research or Theoretical Gap

The theoretical gap in research on children's and youth literature in Indonesia may lie in the lack of in-depth research on trends, issues and the influence of literature on the character formation of the younger generation at the local level. Although there have been several studies that have reviewed this topic, there is still room for further exploration, especially in connecting literary works with the character formation of children and adolescents in more detail and contextually. In addition, the lack of research that combines multidisciplinary approaches can also be a gap in the understanding of children's and youth literature in Indonesia. Approaches involving developmental psychology, sociology, education, and other fields can provide richer insight into how literature influences the character formation of generations of young people. Therefore, the aim of this research is to fill this theoretical gap by conducting a comprehensive analysis of trends, issues and the influence of children's and youth literature in forming the character of the younger generation in Indonesia.

State of the Art

The strength and novelty of this research lies in its commitment to filling the theoretical gaps that exist in research on children's and youth literature in Indonesia. This research promises an in-depth analysis of trends, issues and the influence of literature on the character formation of the younger generation in more detail and contextually and combines a multidisciplinary

approach to provide a better and richer understanding of the impact of literature on the character formation of children and adolescents.

Research Objective

The aim of this research is to determine the influence of children's literature and youth literature on character formation. This study aims to analyze how children's and adolescent literature in Indonesia influences the psychological, social and moral development of children and adolescents. In this research, researchers want to know how the literary themes introduced in children's and adolescent literature influence the behavior and decisions of children and adolescents. Thus, it is hoped that this research will contribute to the development of better curriculum and literary teaching methods in helping Indonesian children and teenagers build better character. And it is also hoped that this research can help the Indonesian community and government in developing more effective educational programs to improve the quality of education and develop the character of the younger generation.

Research Question

1. How do the literary themes introduced in children's and adolescent literature influence the behavior and decisions of children and adolescents?
2. In the context of character formation of the younger generation, how does children's and adolescent literature in Indonesia influence the psychological, social and moral development of children and adolescents?
3. How can analysis of literary themes in children's and youth literature help increase awareness of the Indonesian public and government about the importance of developing the character of the younger generation?

Role of the Researcher

The researcher acts as a researcher who provides information on the topic of children's and youth literature in Indonesia: trends, issues, and their influence on character formation because the researcher is a student who has an academic responsibility to help provide information regarding the problems faced in character formation through children's literature and teenager. The researchers are students and researchers who concentrate on research that focuses on character development.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In a research article, this section clearly outlines the perspective from which the research was conducted, and the specific theories and key concepts underlying the research. Children's Literature Children's literary works are literary works that as far as the language has taste value and as long as the content contains moral educative qualities that can improve the child's mental experience (Winarni, 2014: 2). The quality of children's writing is the result of substances that are adapted to the child's desires and thinking abilities (Huck et al in Nurgiyantoro, 2010:7). Children's literature has the ability to tell everything, even things that adults consider unusual, such as stories of animals that can talk, behave, think and feel like humans. Children's feelings and creative minds are able to understand the story in a natural way, according to their understanding which is shown through their level of understanding.

Youth Literature Youth literature is literary work that explores issues relevant to teenagers and seeks to meet their needs and preferences. The themes, characters and language styles used are adapted to the preferences and personalities of teenagers (Sumardjo, 1982:63). Some terms used to refer to youth literature include chick lit (short for chick literature) and teenlit (short for teen literature), which refers to literature aimed at teenagers.

In an effort to increase learning and discussion resources in literature classes, various materials such as youth novels, comics, youth short stories, popular songs, soap operas and dramas must be used as productive sources. Teachers and educators can engage in the exploration of youth literature in various ways and levels of creativity, to better understand it.

Damhuri Muhammad, a writer, commented on "Current Literary Update Issues". Currently there is a kind of hesitation among writers about digitizing works or texts that are part of the literary ecosystem, some writers believe that only by sharing uploads of new book reviews or links to short stories published on digital platforms. They already feel part of the digital space, but it's just digitizing, the real problem with the digital ocean or big data is different.

Gender issues have an interesting and important role in children's literature, considering the position of that literature. According to Taxel (1995: 159), Children's literature is the result of agreements rooted in the dominant ideology and belief system at the time the work was created. The socio-cultural background of the society in which children are raised greatly influences gender representation in children's literature. It is important to pay attention to the messages conveyed by male and female characters in the story, because this can contribute to shaping children's perceptions regarding what it means to be a boy, girl, adult man or adult woman. How the characters presented in children's stories will influence children's understanding of attitudes and behavior that are in accordance with gender roles accepted in their society.

METHOD

Research Design

The approach used in this research is a qualitative descriptive approach, which is a research method for collecting data in the form of narrative descriptions both verbally and in writing from participants as well as observations of the phenomena observed, according to (J. Lexy in Moleong, 2010:4). Moleong also said that because of its qualitative method, descriptive research focuses on data in the form of data and images rather than numbers. In addition, all information collected may contribute to what has been researched. The research also uses hermeneutic studies to understand the meaning contained in novels and fairy tales. By using this approach, analysis can be used more deeply and accurately and allows researchers to identify the meaning contained in the text and how this meaning influences character formation.

Data Source

Data sources for the purposes of this research by analyzing children's and youth literature, namely popular novels for teenagers such as "Laskar Pelangi" by Andrea Hirata, Sertafables such as "The Mouse Deer and the Turtle". Apart from that, it also utilizes secondary data such as journal articles, research reports, and official documents related to education, literature, and child and adolescent development to support the analysis and interpretation of research results.

Data Collection and Procedure

The data collected was analyzed qualitatively, analysis of findings is presented descriptively in the form of terms, meanings and their application. Documentation and literature study methods are used to collect data that seems appropriate. As part of this analysis the researcher reviewed and recorded various documents collected from initial data relevant to the problem research purposes.

Data Analysis

Got it several stages taken in the process of analyzing this research data, like collecting data in the novel *Laskar Pelangi*: (a). Read carefully the novel *Laskar Pelangi* by Andrea Hirata. (b). Note down the sentences that show it that in the novel *Laskar Pelangi* by Andrea Hirata, as moral values. (c). Describe the results of analysis produce conclusions about moral values and how they influence the formation of character in adolescents. Next, collect data in the fable of the mouse deer and the turtle by Rahimidin Zahari, namely (a). Read carefully the fable of the mouse deer and the turtle (b). Note down the sentences that show the moral values and principles in the fable of the deer and the turtle (c). Displaying the results of the analysis then concluding moral values and their influence on character formation in children

Accuracy

Objectivity in conducting qualitative research is very important to maintain, because researcher subjectivity is often involved in research, thereby damaging the validity of the data. Researcher objectivity also needs to be maintained through accuracy, so that the researcher's position can be controlled in every step and research process. This maintenance effort is carried out by crosschecking data obtained from interviews with school consular officers in collaboration with our students who are doing practical work at the school. They observe subjects more intensely they're at school or even they are in activities outside of school. The researchers realized that maternal or parental feelings sometimes distorted interviews; However, using an interview guide can solve this without involving these feelings. The researcher also applies self-reflection to the first author's profession as a lecturer in Family Psychology courses and the second author who is struggling in educational development. Starting from several writings by the first author about the family and the second author about education, researchers began to develop studies regarding family relations in educational development. Reflecting that continuity is very important in increasing the credibility of qualitative research, so that as researchers we are able to reconsider our vision and passion for research in every step and process.

Trustworthiness

By using qualitative descriptive methods, it can provide in-depth insight into the phenomena studied through direct observation and in-depth analysis. Thus, this research can be trusted because it can produce a rich and detailed understanding of the research subject.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Finding

Literary works can act as a means of catharsis, a concept mentioned by Aristotle, a philosopher and literary expert. According to him, literature not only entertains, but also cleanses the souls

of both the writer and the reader. For readers, reading literary works can open minds and feelings, provide entertainment and insight. Likewise, for writers, creating literary works can be a process of liberation and expression that brings depth and freedom to the soul. In the context of character education, literature can be used passively, namely by receiving and absorbing the messages conveyed, as well as actively by expressing and responding to them. The importance of selecting quality literary works in learning is to ensure that students are exposed to good literary construction and values that enrich and improve their character.

The way that can be used to apply literary works expressively as a tool for character formation is by guiding students in managing various emotional aspects, feelings, enthusiasm, thoughts, ideas and views through creative activities such as writing literary works and participating in films, theater or drama. Children are encouraged to organize their views, ideas, opinions, feelings and emotions, then express them through literary works. Various emotions and feelings, such as dissatisfaction with the existing system, anger, the desire to convey a message, and the like, can be expressed through various literary forms, such as drama, poetry or prose. Of course, choosing the right media is important to change this "soul turmoil", which can be drama, poetry, short stories or novels.

Children's Literature

Children's literature is any type of literary work aimed specifically at children, even though the main theme is not always directly related to children's lives or situations involving them (Supriyadi & Riyadi, 2018). Literature studies for children can include a variety of descriptions of human, animal and plant life. The strength of children's literature lies in its ability to shape characters in an effective way, because the values contained and moral messages in literary works are conveyed through stories and metaphors, not directly. This makes the learning process more enjoyable and does not feel patronizing. Thus, learning literature for children can help develop character in educational institutions.

Fables are a form of literature aimed at children, which tell the stories of the lives of animals that behave like humans. This is a type of fictional story that is not based on a true story. Fables are often known as moral stories, because they convey a moral message or lesson through the story (Narmawati, 2018: 5). The characters in fables generally take the form of animals, but the text of the story not only reflects animal life, but also describes various aspects of human life with all their characteristics. Animals in fables have characteristics similar to humans, including good and bad characters. They can be honest, polite, intelligent, friendly, and perform noble deeds, but on the other hand, there are those who are selfish, deceptive, arrogant, cunning, and fraudulent. The target readers for fable stories are not only children, but also adult readers (Haryadi, 2004).

Based on the results of research conducted on the fable entitled "The Kancil and the Turtle", it is customary to form a character for a child's attitude, namely as teaching material which directly shapes the characteristics and traits of a child. From the rabbit character who has an arrogant nature, we can take it as an example for children not to do bad things like that. We can teach children to always be humble about what we have, because pride and envy will form bad character.

From the story about the mouse deer and the turtle, children can learn that envy and envy are not good. These traits can encourage someone to behave negatively, as the mouse deer did which made other animals hate the turtle. To have many friends, it is important for us to be

sincerely kind to everyone. That way, other people will be happy to be friends with us. On the other hand, evil behavior towards others will bring us disaster and difficulty. This principle reflects the law of karma, that we will reap what we sow. Every good or bad action will have its own reward. These values are very good and have the benefit of forming children's character and can become learning material for children and apply them in their lives.

Youth Literature

Syahrul (2017:9), youth literature, also called teen lit, is a literary work whose contents describe the social life of teenagers. As the name suggests, teen lit depicts teenage stories, including issues such as friendship, romance, and conflict with parents. The characteristic of teen lit is the use of relaxed language and a simple storyline. The teenage lit phenomenon is not only limited to Indonesia, but also occurs in various other countries.

Literary works have the power to convey moral messages that can change the minds and behavior of readers more effectively than lecture methods or violence. Through the reading experience, moral messages are conveyed indirectly into the reader's subconscious, encouraging them to reflect on and internalize the values contained in the literary work. For example, novels can inspire teenagers to emulate the behavior of the characters in the story, triggering positive changes in themselves.

Literature can help improve speaking, bad behavior, and spoken word. Literature provides useful lessons and life experiences. Readers benefit from literary works. Analysis of the value of character education is included in novels, such as Andrea Hirata's novel *Laskar Pelangi*. This novel tells the author's life story. The author's desire to give his teacher something valuable is the background to writing this novel. Books are something valuable because they are considered a luxury during the journey that requires education. This is the author's way of giving appreciation and appreciation to his teachers for their efforts to improve education.

The novel *Laskar Pelangi* shows how brave educators are in carrying out their duties. In their dedication to teaching, Mrs. Muslimah and Mr. Harfan are described as teachers who have noble values and Pancasila values. The school faced many challenges during its journey, and the condition of the school was very worrying (Rismawati, 2022). Andrea Hirata's novel "*Laskar Pelangi*" contains many valuable character education values for students. Among these values include religiosity, love of peace, national spirit, curiosity, democracy, creativity, hard work, discipline, tolerance, honesty, love of the country, appreciation for achievements, friendship, love of reading, environmental awareness, and concern.

The importance of character education values that originate from human values that are reflected in the daily lives of the main characters in the novel "*Laskar Pelangi*" are very suitable to be implemented directly with children. This can be seen from the innate character, words and behavior of the main character in the story, which provides concrete examples of the importance of these values in everyday life.

Discussion

Fable literary works play a diverse role in children's education, not only serving as a source of entertainment but also as a powerful tool for character formation and moral education. They play an important role in developing cognitive and language skills, addressing environmental awareness, and even assisting in psychological assessments. Fables can be a useful instrument

in promoting Gospel morality among children and adults, stimulating visualization and verbal communication.

Novels are a part of literature that has a great ability to influence the attitudes and behavior of readers. Sometimes, novel readers feel emotionally connected to the characters in the story and even have a strong desire to become one of these characters or meet them to get encouragement. This phenomenon occurs because novels have intrinsic and extrinsic elements that make the events depicted in the story feel alive and relevant to the real world.

Literary themes introduced in literary works can significantly influence the behavior and decisions of children and adolescents. Literary works, such as novels and fiction stories, can help children and teenagers understand moral values, emotions and actions that are appropriate to daily routines. In several literary works, themes such as gender equality, masculinity, and feminism can help children and adolescents understand and evaluate gender roles in society. However, it should be remembered that the influence of literary themes on the behavior and decisions of children and adolescents also depends on the context and the way the literary work is introduced.

In the context of character formation of the younger generation, children's and adolescent literature in Indonesia influences the psychological, social and moral development of children and adolescents in the following ways: Psychological Influence: Children's and youth literature can help Indonesian children develop critical thinking and analytical skills, as well as increase their ability to adapt to various situations Social Influence: Children's and youth literature can influence the social behavior of Indonesian children by showing examples of good and bad behavior.

Moral Influence: Children's and youth literature can influence the morals of Indonesian children by displaying positive moral values such as honesty, integrity and awareness. Literary themes in children's and youth literature can help increase awareness of the Indonesian public and government about the importance of developing the character of the younger generation. By studying themes related to adolescent life, such as identity, courage, and honesty, analysis of literary themes can help society, and the government understand the issues facing the younger generation and how to overcome them.

CONCLUSION

Children's and youth literature has an influence on character changes. The values contained are very useful in shaping children's character and can be learning material for children in their daily lives. Themes in literature introduced in literary works can significantly influence the behavior and decisions of children and adolescents. In the context of character formation of the younger generation, children's and adolescent literature in Indonesia influences the psychological, social and moral development of children and adolescents. Apart from that, character education values, especially human values that are reflected in literary characters, are visible in everyday life through the characters' behavior, speech and innate traits. These values can be adopted by children in their daily lives. Children's and youth literature can also help increase awareness of the Indonesian public and government about the importance of developing the character of the younger generation.

Recommendation for Future Research

The author hopes that this research can be strengthened intrinsically and extrinsically. The author hopes that future research will carry out similar research by exploring problems that have not been studied in this current research.

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DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTEREST

The authors expressly declare that there are no potential conflicts of interest that might exist between the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. All research and writings are prepared objectively and transparently, without influence from any party that could influence the results or interpretation of research findings.

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